

ULTRASOUND IN CFRP DETECTED BY ADVANCED OPTICAL FIBER SENSOR FOR COMPOSITE STRUCTURAL HEALTH MONITORING

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ABSTRACT

Various ultrasonic structural health monitoring techniques have been researched to guarantee the safety of composites. In this paper, a highly advanced optical fiber sensor based on phase-shifted fiber Bragg grating was used to detect ultrasound propagating in carbon fiber reinforced plastics. This sensor has shown broad bandwidth and high sensitivity compared to conventional optical sensors. Therefore, it is capable to detect high-frequency ultrasound with small energy. Three different ultrasound-based SHM techniques, including Acousto-ultrasonic detection, acoustic emission and nonlinear ultrasonic detection, were tried to demonstrate the advantages of this technique in evaluation of diversified damages inside the composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite materials, in particular carbon fibre reinforced plastics (CFRPs), have played an important role in ensuring a low carbon consumption as they are well suited to and have been widely used in many important industrial sectors, such as in aerospace, automotive and construction, due to their unique features of being lightweight, high strength, and corrosion-resistance. However, they suffer from micro-damage features which not only can decrease the strength of the composite but also develop, eventually leading to the catastrophic material failure and with that loss of the structure itself and potentially loss of life. To address the challenges of producing better and more resilient structures, a number of structural health monitoring (SHM) techniques have been used both by the industry and by the scientific community, for example, in which PZT-based ultrasonic sensing has been recognized as one of the most important solutions as it can both provide real-time detection and cover a wider measurement range compared to the other strain-based sensing techniques. There are problems however in that such ultrasonic sensors are usually of bulky and heavy-weight, making it difficult for them to be integrated effectively into real composite structures to allow better real-time monitoring. Therefore, we proposed and then demonstrated a novel optical fibre ultrasonic sensor system. Compared to conventional optical fiber sensors, such as fiber Bragg grating sensor that has been used in acousto-ultrasonic detection, this novel sensor has shown its stronger capabilities in other more advanced ultrasonic SHM techniques, including acoustic emission (AE) detection and nonlinear ultrasonic detection. Such an optical fiber sensor with its ultrasonic SHM technique is designed to allowing for early, and highly effective action to be taken to minimize both the damage and the significant costs and potential for loss of life associated with the late repair or even catastrophic material failure.

This paper is organized in four parts. After the background is introduced, the sensor proposed and its calibration results will be explained in section 2. In section 3, three different ultrasonic SHM techniques, the frequency of which increases from hundreds kHz to MHz, have been tried based on the usage of this sensor, showing its broad application fields. Then, the last part is the conclusion.

2 PHASE-SHIFTED FIBER BRAGG GRATING BALANCED SENSOR

2.1 Phase-shifted fiber Bragg grating

Figure 1 shows the PSFBG balanced sensor we designed. The key components in this sensing system is the PSFBG, fabricated by Fujikura Ltd., which receives the ultrasonic signal. It is manufactured by inserting a π phase shift in the center of a normal optical fiber grating. As a consequence, in the center of its reflective spectrum, a sharp dip is generated, which benefits to enhance the ultrasonic detection sensitivity, as shown in Fig. 1(a). This phase-shift design also enlarges the ultrasonic detectable bandwidth due to its ultra-short effective grating length [1]. Besides these two merits, the PSFBG with diameter of $150\ \mu\text{m}$ and length of $5\ \text{mm}$ is much smaller than a conventional PZT sensor, leading to its embedding ability, as shown in Fig. 1(b).

Figure 1: Phase-shifted fiber Bragg grating balanced sensor. (a) PSFBG spectrum; (b) comparison between the conventional PZT sensor and advanced PSFBG sensor; (c) Balanced demodulation system.

2.2 Balanced sensing system

The other important innovation in this sensing design is the balanced demodulation technique, as shown in Fig. 1(c). Conventional techniques only use the reflected light or transmitted light. Our technique, however, simultaneously detects the reflected and transmitted light by the balanced photodetector (New Focus, 2117). Then, the photodetector converts the optical light change to electric signals, which is subsequently recorded by oscilloscope (Yokogawa, DL708E) or other data acquisition system. In this process, the ultrasonic signal is doubled but the noise, especially the laser noise, is reduced. As a result, the balanced demodulation system can further enhance the ultrasonic detection sensitivity [2]. In the actual application of this system, we also added a feedback controller to precisely lock the wavelength of the tunable laser (Agilent, 81682A) to the 3-dB position on the slope of the PSFBG spectrum. A variety of data process methods were also designed to analyze the ultrasonic signals to meet the requirement of specific application field.

2.3 Performance of the system

Before detecting ultrasound propagating in composite, we validated the performance of this system on an aluminum plate by using acousto-ultrasonic setup. The input signal was continuous ultrasound with different frequencies, and the received signal was monitored in an electric spectrum analyzer (Advantest, R3131A). Fig. 2 shows the comparison results. Traditional PZT sensor has broad bandwidth up to $5\ \text{MHz}$ and has the lowest noise level (perhaps lower than the detectability of the electrical spectrum analyzer). However, this PZT sensor is insensitive to the signal from 2 to $3\ \text{MHz}$. This piezoelectric materials' intrinsic resonant phenomenon, namely uneven responses to each frequency components, may affect further signal analysis. The detected signal of the conventional FBG sensor is weak, and cannot be clearly distinguished from the noise when the frequency is higher

than 1 MHz. Megahertz bandwidth and PZT-comparable sensitivity are necessary for nonlinear ultrasonic SHM, conventional FBG sensor is thus not suitable. In contrast, the ultrasonic response of the PSFBG is much higher than that of FBG, and is smoother than that of PZT. Furthermore, the novel PSFBG balanced sensor enhances the signal-to-noise ratio (sensitivity) further to a PZT-comparable level after doubling the signal and rejecting the noise. This high sensitivity makes AE-based SHM detection that needs real-time detection possible. The broad and smooth frequency response of the PSFBG balanced sensor is also helpful to detect both fundamental and harmonic Lamb wave with small bias in nonlinear ultrasonic detection. In summary, the characteristics of the PSFBG balanced sensor could benefit the following ultrasonic detection for SHM of composites.

Figure 2: Comparison among different sensors demonstrates the high performance of the PSFBG balanced sensor. Solid line is the signal power, and the dot line is the noise level.

3 ULTRASONIC STRUCTURAL HEALTH MONITORING

3.1 Acousto-ultrasonic detection

Firstly, an acousto-ultrasonic detection using the setup shown in Fig. 3 (a) was conducted. In this experiment, a CFRP laminate with layup of $[0_2/90/2]_s$ was used. A resonant PZT actuator (Fuji Ceramics, M31) with a diameter of 3 mm and height of 3 mm was used to generate simulated ultrasonic waves. The voltage signal with peak-to-peak voltages of 20 V input into the PZT actuator was a one-cycle sinusoidal wave at 500 kHz with a Hamming window generated by a function generator (NF, WF1974). The ultrasonic wave was received by the optical fiber sensor and a PZT sensor 40 mm apart from the PZT actuator. The PZT sensor was glued by a high-acoustic-impedance ultrasonic couplant. The PSFBG was attached by applying cyanoacrylate adhesive near the grating area of the PS-FBG to create a cantilever structure. This gluing method used in this experiment have been proved that it does not affect the characteristics of the ultrasonic signal, but can decrease the influences from environmental disturbances, such as temperature change and small vibration [3]. This gluing method is also used in the following AE detection and nonlinear detection.

Fig. 3(b) shows the waveforms detected by the PSFBG and PZT sensor. Both sensors succeeded in detecting the ultrasonic waves. In Fig. 3(b), both waves arrive at the same time, but the waveforms are different. FBG is mainly sensitive to the horizontal strain, whereas the PZT sensor is mainly sensitive to the vertical strain. On the other hand, the ultrasonic waves propagated in the CFRP laminates are Lamb waves with extensional modes and flexural modes. Thus, the waveforms detected by the PSFBG and PZT sensor are usually different.

The spectra in Fig. 3(c) show the root mean square amplitude of the corresponding signals detected by the PSFBG and PZT sensor, calculated by Fast Fourier transform and then normalization. Although the waveforms are different, the spectra of both detected waveforms have similar broad bandwidths covered by the spectrum of the input signal and have peak frequencies of approximately 500 kHz. Based on the spectrum, it is also clear that the noise level obtained by the PSFBG is 5 dB higher than that obtained by the PZT sensor. In other words, the sensitivity of the PSFBG is only 5 dB lower than that of the PZT sensor, which is a very high sensitivity for high-frequency ultrasonic signals.

Figure 3: Acousto-ultrasonic detection. (a) experimental setup, (b) time domain signals, (c) corresponding spectra.

3.2 Acoustic emission detection

Figure 4(a) shows the setup for the AE detection in a tensile testing. In this experiment, CFRP laminates with tabs were stretched by a material testing machine (Shimadzu AG-50 kNG). In addition to the PSFBG and PZT sensor for AE signals detection, two strain gages were glued on both surfaces of the CFRP laminates to monitor the strains. The strains were recorded by a data logger (Keyence, NR-ST04).

Figure 4: Acoustic emission detection. (a) experimental setup, (b) energy distribution of the AE signals in the tensile test. (c) transverse cracks and fiber breaking of the laminate.

The Kaiser effect is an important and unique phenomenon in AE detections as a result of the physical nature of AE because AE signals are produced when the loaded strain exceeds the previous level. To verify the Kaiser effect, the load of the tensile testing machine used in the AE detection experiment had continuous triangle shapes. When the load from the tensile testing machine was generated, both the AE hits and strain information were collected. The total duration of this experiment was 385 s, ending when the CFRP laminate was broken.

The thresholds of AE detection used in this experiment were set as 51 dB and 48 dB for the PSFBG and PZT sensor, respectively. These thresholds were determined when no background noise was detected for one minute when the CFRP laminate was placed in the static experimental environment. The 3-dB higher threshold for PSFBG can be explained by the higher noise level in PSFBG, as explained in the last section.

During this AE experiment, thousands of signals were recorded that containing noise signals, such as low vibration, or frictions between the tab and jig. We have developed a sophisticated data process method to eliminate the noises, and then showed the signal energy distribution vs time in Fig. 4(b). The total number of AE hits for the PSFBG and PZT sensor are 657 and 971, respectively. Although the AE number detection by PSFBG is smaller than that detected by PZT, this result is much better than previous reported results. Because it is clear that AE signals only exhibited when the strain exceeded previous maximal value, the Kaiser effect is demonstrated solidly. By analyzing different energy distribution of the AE signals, we also can discriminate different damage types in the CFRP laminate. From 0-360 s, the AE signals have energy lower than 10^3 , corresponding to damages that emit low energy that is thought to be transverse cracks. In the end of the experiment when strain level is high, the AE signals have much higher energy levels, which may correspond to fiber breakings. The demonstration of Kaiser effect and damage discrimination also can be analyzed from the viewpoint of accumulative AE hits [4].

To verify the different types of damage described above, one additional specimen was linearly stretched to the low strain level of 8 me. In this case, we observed the edge of this CFRP laminate using a microscope (Olympus, BH-2). The transverse cracking was successfully observed, as shown in the first photo of Fig. 4(c). The other photo of Fig. 4(c) was taken when the first CFRP laminate was damaged, clearly revealing the fiber breaking. According to these observations, we confirmed that the two damage types in CFRP laminates, i.e., transverse crack and fiber breaking, appeared at different strain levels.

3.3 Nonlinear ultrasonic detection

Acousto-ultrasonic detection is not sensitive to transverse cracks in composite. AE detection can detect ultrasound generated by cracks but once it cannot evaluate the existing cracks since it is a passive SHM technique. On the other hand, nonlinear ultrasonic technique provides the possibility of transverse crack evaluation because its ability in monitoring fatigue crack growth in an aluminum plate has been demonstrated [5]. Figure 5 shows the experiment setup. A CFRP laminate with the same layup as the one used in AE experiment was loaded step-by-step in a tensile test in order to generate transverse cracks gradually. Two PZT sensors and the PSFBG sensor were glued on the same surface of the laminate. During tensile test, these two PZT sensors functioned as AE sensors to precisely evaluate the increasing number of the transverse cracks. In 18 steps, the loading force has increased to 10.4 kN, and the transverse crack AE signal evaluated is approximately 20.

In each step when the tensile test stopped, one as an actuator generated continuous ultrasound with frequency of 0.5 MHz, while the other detected it to provide reference. The designed optical fiber sensor also received the continuous ultrasonic signals. By conducting Fast Fourier Transform to the detected signals, their spectra are shown in Fig. 5(b) and (c), respectively. In both figures, there exist higher order harmonic signals besides the fundamental signal. The successful detection of the harmonic signal means this optical fiber sensor has large potential in nonlinear SHM. The second-order harmonic signal that we pay attention to was caused by the breathing effects of the transverse cracks when fundamental wave propagates through it. When the cracks increase during the tensile test, the amplitude change of the harmonic frequency peak was observed, showing relations between transverse crack number and nonlinear parameters, which will be researched further in the future.

Figure 5: Nonlinear ultrasonic signals. (a) Experimental setup, (b) spectrum of the ultrasound detected by the PSFBG, (c) spectrum of the ultrasound detected by the PZT sensor.

4 CONCLUSION

In this paper, a newly designed PSFBG balanced sensor was used in three different ultrasonic SHM techniques to monitoring the health status of composite materials. In acousto-ultrasonic detection, this sensor real-time detected ultrasonic signals, covering similar frequency range and having same arrival time compared to the signal detected by PZT sensor. In AE detection, the detected signal demonstrated Kaiser effect successfully and helped to discriminate two different damage types that are transverse crack and fiber breaking. In nonlinear ultrasonic detection, higher order harmonic frequency was detected, showing its potential in evaluation of the transverse crack numbers in CFRP laminates. In conclusion, the novel PSFBG balanced sensor can give reliable results in multiple ultrasonic SHM application fields.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Q. Wu and Y. Okabe, Ultrasonic sensor employing two cascaded phase-shifted fiber Bragg gratings suitable for multiplexing, *Optics letters*, **37**, 2012, pp. 3336-3338.
- [2] Q. Wu and Y. Okabe, High-sensitivity ultrasonic phase-shifted fiber Bragg grating balanced sensing system, *Optics Express*, **20**, 2012, pp. 28353-28362.
- [3] F.-m. Yu, Y. Okabe, Q. Wu, and N. Shigeta, A novel method of identifying damage types in carbon fiber-reinforced plastic cross-ply laminates based on acoustic emission detection using a fiber-optic sensor, *Composites Science and Technology*, **135**, 2016, pp. 116-122.
- [4] Q. Wu, F. Yu, Y. Okabe, and S. Kobayashi, Application of a novel optical fiber sensor to detection of acoustic emissions by various damages in CFRP laminates, *Smart Materials and Structures*, **24**, 2015, p. 015011.
- [5] C. Zhou, M. Hong, Z. Su, Q. Wang, and L. Cheng, Evaluation of fatigue cracks using nonlinearities of acousto-ultrasonic waves acquired by an active sensor network, *Smart Materials and Structures*, **22**, 2013, p. 015018.